

Publishing Guidance for Astera-funded Work

Astera's vision & expectations

We envision a future in which all research outputs are shared rapidly and openly. The journal publication system is fundamentally unfit for this purpose and is a relic of the past. In an effort to build for a more abundant, open future, Astera will no longer support this journal-centric world. Explicitly, we will not allow Astera time or funds to be used to contribute directly to journal articles.

This constraint is an intentional forcing function for researchers to try new and better ways to continuously publish as much of their work as possible in the form of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) research outputs. Astera also supports the cataloging and documentation of these outputs to enhance interpretability. Within this framework, we seek to maximize the potential for broad reach, impact, and reuse. We realize there's no perfect solution yet, and will be working with researchers to experiment and innovate towards a better future.

We understand that pushing against the status quo for publishing can sometimes be challenging or uncomfortable. In the absence of proxies for quality (journal titles or impact factors, for example) demonstrating reach and impact are more difficult. But the substance of quality and rigor is more important than the appearance of it.

These guidelines exemplify Astera's vision and [core principles](#), and keep us accountable so that we remain radically transparent. We look forward to working with researchers to be changemakers for open science.

Primary outputs

Researchers are expected to:

- Publish outputs as soon as they are ready for reuse. All underlying outputs (code, data, presentations, etc) must be openly published when or before (1) they are referenced publicly or (2) the findings are shared with Astera in a written report.
- Apply appropriate licenses/waivers (see below).
- Deposit research outputs in venues that ensure outputs are FAIR (see below). ● List Astera as an affiliation or a funder, using its Research Organization Registry (ROR) ID when this becomes available.
- Maintain a list of research outputs in a spreadsheet that is shared with the open science team. We will provide a template.

Researchers are prohibited from:

- Using Astera funds or time to contribute (whether as an author or otherwise) directly to the creation of journal publications.
- Listing Astera as an affiliation on any journal article.

- Delaying publication of Astera-funded outputs of any kind to accommodate journal articles.
- Using Astera funding for publication fees.
- Using Astera funding or time for research intended to satisfy journal reviewers and editors.

Types of outputs

Below are our current recommended FAIR venues for publishing research outputs at Astera. Researchers should reach out to Prachee Avasthi (prachee@astera.org) to explore anything that isn't represented here.

Code - MIT license or more open

- [GitHub*](#)

Data - CC0 waiver

- [Zenodo*](#)
- When there is a disciplinary repository available that would make content more visible and impactful, please discuss with Prachee Avasthi (prachee@astera.org).

Articles/text - CC BY or more open

- [Nanopublications](#) (for hypotheses and other assertions)
- Preprint servers such as [bioRxiv](#)
- Posts without a DOI and permanent archiving (eg. [Substack](#), [Medium](#), etc) should be archived on Zenodo

Protocols - CC BY or more open

- [Protocols.io](#)
- Other approved repositories, such as Zenodo**

Physical resources

- [Addgene](#)
- [DSMZ](#)

*Astera may enable community lists or channels when there is sufficient need

**to request approvals, please reach out to Prachee Avasthi (prachee@astera.org)

Making research outputs interpretable

As we move away from a paradigm that centers around journal articles, we must find new ways to describe and organize continuously-published research outputs so that they are interpretable.

We recognize that this and other open research practices come at the cost of time and other

resources. Astera is working to develop tools that will make this process easier. For now, researchers are expected to maintain a list of research outputs they have created as part of their work with Astera in a spreadsheet.

We look forward to a world where policies like this one are unnecessary, because they embody default practices. We're excited to contribute to creating that better future.

Frequently Asked Questions

If you have questions not addressed on this list, please reach out to Prachee Avasthi.

What about data embargoes and sensitive data (relating to privacy or security concerns)?

In general, delaying the publication of data runs counter to Astera's values, but we recognize that certain situations may necessitate a more closed approach. Please contact Prachee to discuss your individual case.

What are some examples of how I can collaborate with others with different publishing goals?

If Astera researchers are collaborating with an outside group that wishes to publish in journals, we recommend that the Astera researchers FAIRly and promptly publish their related findings (figures, data, text, code etc) according to this updated Astera policy. The academic group can then reuse and appropriately cite these materials in a manuscript to be submitted to a journal. If the journal objects on the grounds that the work has been previously published, we recommend that the group look up the journal's preprint policy: the partial release of material included in the manuscript is akin to the publication of a preprint.

What if there's something I want to protect IP for?

All IP created during employment or under contract is owned by Astera, and we will publish it appropriately to maximize social benefit.

What about my or other peoples' careers?

Fears about career progression have propped up the current scientific publishing system. While we understand this is a concern for many, we want to redesign publishing to maximize societal impact. Therefore, individual career concerns are secondary to impact in our considerations. We understand that this may limit who chooses to work with us, but we believe there is still a considerable talent pool that is aligned with our priorities and doesn't view our open science approach as an intolerable trade-off.

It's also worth considering whether these fears are overblown. For example, rather than a winner-take-all approach, [citations to scooping and scooped papers are nearly equal \(56-44 split\)](#). The increased visibility and impact that open approaches provide may

increase (rather than decrease) your reputation in a field.

What if my work would benefit from peer review?

Peer review can take many forms, and we are interested in improving this part of the publishing process to increase rigor and reuse. For example, review can happen openly after publication of a preprint. You can engage with initiatives such as PREreview, Review Commons, Peer Community In, and more to organize this.

What if my field is really small and I can't compel others to do this?

In a small field, your efforts will have even greater impact. Reach out to the open science team so that we can help you brainstorm how to take advantage of this.

What if someone else takes my published data and reuses it towards a journal publication later?

If the journal authors cite your published data, this is an example of the system working as intended. If the authors have used your work without attribution, consider contacting the editors to explore issuing a correction.

What if someone uses my tool or platform to generate results that are published in a journal? If the journal authors cite your tool or platform, this is an example of the system working as intended. If the authors have used your work without attribution, consider contacting the editors to explore issuing a correction.

What if I leave Astera in the middle of a project before I'm ready to publish?

All work product created during employment or under contract is property of Astera, and we will publish it appropriately to maximize social benefit. Consult with Prachee to create a plan for publishing your outputs.

Can I post my short observations to a preprint server?

Yes. Different preprint servers have different submissions standards. For example, bioRxiv is for "complete, unpublished" manuscripts that contain new data, but there are very short bioRxiv preprints with one or even zero figures or tables ([FAQ](#)). On the other hand, [OSF Preprints](#) hosts many communities that moderate submissions, but users can also submit a preprint outside of these communities, and it will be posted immediately.

You can also use preprint servers to publish "preprints in progress" that update over time. Please see [Navarro & Cheeseman](#) as an example.

If your observations are more like a single data point or assertion, consider [nanopublications](#). These machine-readable objects can be used to express hypotheses (see [example](#)). Journals can sometimes help people find my work more easily. What are some other ways to do this in the absence of journals?

Great question. We strongly recommend you explore other strategies that allow you to increase

visibility of your work with more author agency. For instance, you can communicate with broader communities via social media, Substack, etc.

What if I've already committed to things this policy now forbids?

Consult with Prachee if you need assistance.